

O'ZBEKISTON BRIOFLORASI TARKIBIDAGI DORIVOR BRIOFITLAR

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Annotatsiya: Briofitlar an'anaviy tibbiyotda ahamiyatli bo'lib, 150 ga yaqin etnobotanik turlari butun dunyoda tan olingan. Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston brioflorasi tarkibida uchraydigan dunyo xalqlarining an'anaviy tibbiyotida foydalanilgan 20 ta dorivor briofitlar ro'yxati keltirilib, har birining qanday kasalliklarga qarshi qo'llanilishi ko'rsatilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Brioflora, O'zbekiston, tibbiyot, kasallik, *Brachythecium rutabulum*.

Аннотация: Мохообразные имеют важное значение в традиционной медицине, и около 150

этноботанических видов признаны во всем мире.

В этой статье перечислены 20 лекарственных мохообразных, которые входят в состав бриофлоры Узбекистана и используются в традиционной медицине народов мира.

Ключевые слова: Бриофлора, Узбекистан, медицина, болезнь, *Brachythecium rutabulum*. **Abstract:** Bryophytes are important in traditional medicine, and about 150 ethnobotanical species

are recognized worldwide. This article lists 20 medicinal bryophytes that are part of the bryoflora of Uzbekistan and are used in traditional medicine of the peoples of the world.

Key words: Bryoflora, Uzbekistan, medicine, disease, *Brachythecium rutabulum*.

O'zbekiston florasida briofitlarni hisobga olmaganda 4380 ga yaqin yuksak o'simliklar turi mavjud bo'lib, ulardan 1200 tasi dorivorligi aniqlangan (Tojiboev va boshqalar, 2014) (Xodjimotov, 2021). O'zbekistonning turli dorivor o'simliklari farmakologik xususiyatlari, yuqori va turlarga boyligi tufayli yangi dori vositalarini kashf qilish imkoniyatiga ega (Egamberdieva va Jabborova, 2018). Ushbu o'simliklardan an'anaviy tibbiyotda foydalanish tobora kengayib borayotgan bo'lsa-da, Respublikamizda uchraydigan briofitlarning o'ziga xos shifobaxsh xususiyatlari keng o'rganilmagan va ulardan an'anaviy yoki ilmiy tibbiyotda qo'llanilishi haqida kam ma'lumot mavjud. Respublikamizda uchraydigan dorivor briofitlar orasida Marchantiophyta va Bryophyta bo'limlariga mansub ayrim turlarning fotosuratlari.

Marchantia polymorpha L.- (MP)

Pellia epiphylla (L.) Corda - (PE)

Brachythecium rutabulum (Hedw.)
Schimp. - (BR)

Funaria hygrometrica Hedw.- (FH)

1-rasm. (MP, PE), - Marchantiophyta, (BR, FH)- Bryophyta bo'limiga mansub.

Quyida hozirgi kunda O'zbekiston brioflorasida shu kungacha aniqlangan dorivor briofitlar ro'yxati keltirilgan bo'lib har bir turni dunyo xalqlari qaysi kasallikni davolashda ishlatilishi qaysi mamlakatlarda foydalanilganligi haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Ammo ushbu turlar ming yillar davomida foydalanishiga qaramay bizning mamlakatimizda ushbu dorivor briofitlardan kasalliklarga qarshi foydalanilganligi haqida ma'lumotlar uchramaydi. Quyida (1-jadval) dorivor briofitlarning 20 turi keltirilib, har bir turning qanday kasalliklarga qo'llanilishi ko'rsatilgan.

1-jadval

O'zbekiston brioflorasi tarkibida bo'lgan, dunyo xalqlarining an'anaviy tibbiyotidagi qo'llaniladigan

briofitlar ro'yxati.

№	Tur	Ananaviy tibbiyotda briofitlardan foydalangan davlatlar	Qo'llanilishi	Adabiyot manbasi
1	<u>Pellia epiphylla</u>	<u>Turkiya</u>	<u>Antibakterial</u>	Akatın et al, (2022).

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2	<u>Riccia fluitans</u>	<u>Yevropa</u>	<u>Teri kasalligida</u>	Tosun et al, (2013).
3	Bryum argenteum	Xitoy Amerika Yevropa	Yallig'lanish va isitmaga qarshi, Zaharlanishga qarshi, Zamburug'larga qarshi	Frahm, (2004) Asakawa, (2007)
4	Bryum capillare	Amerika	Og'riq va isitmani davolash, Kuyishda, Zambrug'li infeksiyaga qarshi	Costică et al, (2023).
5	Barbula unguiculate	Hindiston	Og'riq va isitmani	Costica et al,2023
6	Brachyheclum rutabulum	Hindiston	Kasishda, Kuyishda, Wounds	PantandTewari, (1989)
7	Brachythecium salebrosum	Yevropa	Yuqori antibiotik faolligi uchun	Frahm, (2004) Asakawa, (2007)
8	Ceratodon purpureus	Yevropa	Zambrug'li infeksiyaga qarshi	Asakawa, (2007)
9	Cratoneuron filicinum	Xitoy	Yurak	Costică et al, (2023).

		Hindiston	kasalliklari	Asakawa, (2007)
10	Philonoti sfontana	Hindiston	Yallig'lanish va isitmaga qarshi, Tonzolitda	Costică et al, (2023).
11	Polytrichum commune	Xitoy Amerika Hindiston	Zaharlanishga qarshi, O'pka tuberkulozida, Toshmalarda, Gemostatik, bachadon prolapsasi, Sochni parvarish qilish	Cheng et al, (2012); Costică et al, (2023).
12	Hypnum cupressiforme	Yevropa	Zamburug'larga qarshi	Costică et al, (2023).

Jadvaldan ma'lumki ushbu manbalarda yozilishicha og'ir xastaliklar, yalig'lanishlar, zaharlanish, mikroba va zamburug'larga qarshi, hattoki yurak ishi hamda buyrak yo'llaridan toshlarni yuvuvchi ta'sirga ega bo'lgan noyob dorivor turlar bizning mintaqamizda o'sishi aniqlandi.

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